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³ The initials of the revising individual in capital letters

Deliverable D3.10

Review of how European fishing fleets in international and SFPA waters are managed and conducted

12/07/2021

Executive Summary

This report contains a journal manuscript analysing the development in four bilateral fisheries access agreements that the EU has made with non-member coastal states in terms of monitoring, control and surveillance (MCS). The four bilateral fisheries access agreements, today termed Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreements (SFPAs) are: the agreement with Capo Verde, Mauritania, Senegal, and the Seychelles. The study analyses the changes in the access agreements over time and how the reforms in the CFP (in 1992, 2002 and 2013) and accompanying changes in regulations addressing the external dimension of the EU fleet, are enshrined in the fisheries access agreements. In addition, some considerations are made on how implementation challenges are reflected in the development of the agreements. The focus is on the formal development of the agreements and how new MCS requirements are introduced and operationalized. The study finds a clear strengthening in the MCS provisions in the EU access agreements over time. The provisions generally follow the development in the CFP and accompanying implementing regulations, in some cases also preceding the enshrinement in EU regulations. At the same time, the analysis shows that even though there is a positive development in the MCS requirements in the agreements, the implementation of new requirements can be slow. The study concludes that on the one hand, this gradual and slow implementation might be a viable approach and a way for the EU to be able to implement its external fisheries policy, in particular when accompanied with capacity building initiatives and increased cooperation. On the other hand, if the MCS requirements are not implemented, and are not adjusted to the actual situation, they may end up as paper-regulations which over time will undermine the credibility of the access agreements.

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1 Introduction

This report is the second deliverable of Task 3.1 within the FarFish project, which focuses on analysing the governance of the EU external fishing fleet, that is vessels flagged in EU Member States fishing outside EU waters. FarFish analyses four bilateral fisheries access agreements, today termed Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreements (SFPAs): the agreement with Capo Verde, Mauritania, Senegal, and the Seychelles. The deliverable is a manuscript for a scientific journal and analyses the development in the four agreements in terms of monitoring, control and surveillance (MCS) of the fisheries. The study analyses the changes in the access agreements over time and how the reforms in the CFP (in 1992, 2002 and 2013) and accompanying changes in regulations addressing the external dimension of the EU fleet are enshrined in the fisheries access agreements. In addition, some considerations are made on how implementation challenges are reflected in the development of the agreements. The focus is on the formal development of the agreements and how new MCS requirements are introduced and operationalized. The study therefore presents the main achievements (related to MCS) of the EU fisheries access agreements, and how the EU is able to implement its policy on the external dimension of the CFP related to MCS of fisheries access agreements.

Chapter 2 contains the paper.

2 From Pay Fish Go to Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreements – an analysis of the development in EU fisheries access agreements

Introduction

The European Union (EU) has had bilateral fisheries agreements with countries in Africa and the Pacific for more than 40 years. The agreements were negotiated in the wake of the development in the international law of the sea and the coastal states' establishment of 200 nautical miles Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZs). The EEZ "deprived" the European, and other countries', long distance fleets the right to fish outside the coast of other countries. The conclusion of bilateral access agreements with other countries enabled the long distance fleet of the EU Member States to continue their fishing activities in these areas.⁴ The agreements provide fishing opportunities for a specified time period, usually four years after which they have to be prolonged or renegotiated. The fishing rights are mainly for tuna and tuna-like species, but also pelagic and demersal species within the EEZ of the partner country, and this is provided in exchange for financial compensation. The first agreement was signed with Senegal in 1979, and since then more than 30 agreements have been negotiated. Today, 13 agreements are in force, in addition to 7 dormant agreements.⁵

The EU has a big external fishing fleet, with more than 700 vessels fishing in non-EU waters.⁶ The fleet is fishing on the high seas and in the EEZ of other countries based on public or private agreements. The public agreements are either mutual access agreements with neighbouring states with shared stocks, so called northern agreements, or access agreements with countries mainly in Africa and in around the Pacific and Indian Oceans where the EU pay for fishing rights, of which the latter is under scrutiny in this study. Of the 700 vessels, about 240 from 10 EU Member States are today authorized to fish under these bilateral access agreements.⁷ Vessels operating under Spanish, French and Portuguese flags represent about 94% of the fishing effort. The financial contribution from the EU is today comprised of two elements; a payment for access rights to the third country's EEZ and a financial

⁴ The terms EU fleet/vessels and fleet/vessel of Member States are used interchangeably, as is external fleet and long distance fleet

⁵ Retrieved from https://ec.europa.eu/fisheries/cfp/international/agreements_en

⁶ Retrieved from https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/MEMO_15_6267

⁷ Retrieved from <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/c8b5d962-0d38-11e7-8a35-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-37907030>. In addition to the fisheries taking place under bilateral agreements between the EU and the third countries, European vessels are fishing in other countries under private agreements between the vessel owner and the coastal state, as joint ventures, or by fishing under a non-EU flag. These fisheries are not covered by this study.

assistance known as sectoral support to strengthen the capacity of the third country to manage their fisheries sustainably. In addition, the vessels are to pay a set amount per tonnage caught.

The agreements have been subject to significant changes during these 40 years, from being purely “pay-fish-go” agreements to including provisions about mutual benefit and partnership as well as sustainable management (Van den Bossche and van der Burgt 2009; Sobrino Hereida and Oanta 2015). The agreements are therefore no longer termed access agreements, but Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreements (SFPAs). The changes have come about due to heavy criticism and are embodied in the regular reforms of the European Common Fisheries Policy (CFP) and regulation of the external dimension of the EU fishing fleet (Witbooi 2008; Sobrino Heredia and Oanta 2015). Other studies have examined the performance of these agreements, where their transparency, sustainability, equity and limited economic benefit for the partner countries have been questioned (see for instance Okechukwu 1995; Kaczynski and Fluharty 2001; Stilwell et al. 2010; Nagel and Grey 2012; Gagern and van den Bergh 2013; Le Manach et al. 2013a; 2013b; Hammarlund and Andersson 2019). In this study, it is the development of the agreements itself that is to be examined and how they have developed related to the monitoring, control and surveillance (MCS) of the fisheries. FAO (2002) has defined MCS as all efforts to ensure compliance with fishery management measures, including collection and analysis of data about the fishing activity (e.g. catch, species, fishing effort, bycatch, discard, fishing area), legislative instruments specifying the terms and conditions for fishing (e.g. on licensing, permitted fishing gear, species and fish size, catch limits, bycatch limits, control mechanisms), and the implementation or enforcement through preventive and deterrent mechanisms. As such, MCS are means to the overall objective of ensuring that these agreements are sustainable. The EUs own evaluations have generally and repeatedly concluded that the MCS of its external fishing fleet (as well as other foreign and domestic fleets) operating in these waters is poor (Le Manach 2014). However, since the adoption of the first bilateral access agreements, the provisions on MCS have been substantially strengthened and become more detailed, as has its implementation. The question raised in this paper is therefore, how have these Agreements developed over time in relation to MCS?

Research questions and methods

To analyse the development of the MCS of fisheries taking place under fisheries access agreements, three set of questions are examined: i) What changes are observed in the access agreements over time, ii) How are the reforms in the CFP (in 1992, 2002 and 2013) and accompanying changes in regulations addressing the external dimension of the EU fleet enshrined in the fisheries access agreements; and iii) How are implementation challenges reflected in the development of the agreements? These questions will form the basis for analysing the formal development of the agreements and how new MCS requirements are introduced and operationalized. This allows for a discussion of what achievements (related to MCS) have been made in the EU fisheries access

agreements, and how the EU is able to implement its policy on the external dimension of the CFP related to MCS of fisheries access agreements.

The analysis is based on document analysis of fisheries access agreements.⁸ The agreements are based on the same format and consist of a framework agreement laying down general guidelines, with corresponding protocols and annexes specifying the more detailed terms and conditions. These include amongst others, provisions on MCS, financial contribution and sectoral support, and the cooperation between the coastal state and the EU as well as with the economic actors (i.e., community vessels). In addition, the publicly available ex-post/ex-ante evaluations of the agreements carried out before renegotiating a new agreement⁹ have been used to support the analysis. Agreements with four countries were selected for the study: Cape Verde, Mauritania, Senegal, and the Seychelles. The agreements cover both tuna- and non-tuna/mixed agreements, and agreements in both the Atlantic and Indian Ocean. All agreements are in force and all have been renegotiated several times. The analysis therefore covers agreements negotiated under different CFPs. This allows for an inter-generational comparison of the agreements following the CFP reforms in 1992, 2002 and 2013, in addition to comparison of agreements between countries, including both tuna and mixed/non-tuna agreements. The total number of agreements analysed in each case differ, but all cover the time period from the pay-fish-go agreements in the 1990s through FPA in 2002 and finally to SFPA in 2013. The starting point of the analysis is the evolution of the CFPs related to the external dimension. This is based on analysis of the CFPs, EU reports and papers related to the reforms, and the MCS regulations (e.g., the Control Regulation, the Fisheries Authorizations Regulation, and the IUU-Regulation)¹⁰, in addition to scientific analysis of the CFP reforms and their impact on EUs external fisheries policy and the SFPAs. The tuna fisheries taking place under the access agreements are also governed by the Regional Fisheries Management Organisations ICCAT (the International Commission on the conservation of Atlantic Tuna) and IOTC (Indian Ocean Tuna Commission), to which the EU and the four partner countries are members. The MCS requirements pertaining from these falls outside the scope of this analysis, where the access agreements and how they have developed in relation to the CFP are under scrutiny.

Structure of the paper

The next section gives a brief overview of the development of the EUs governance of its vessels operating outside community waters. The rationale behind and output of the regular reforms of the CFP related to the fisheries in the waters of partner countries will be outlined, as well as associated regulations, the so-called implementing pillars of the external dimension of the EU fisheries policy mentioned above. Based on this, a review of the development in the four fisheries access agreements

⁸ Retrieved from the EU law database <http://eur-lex.europa.eu>

⁹ Retrieved from the webpage of DG Mare: https://ec.europa.eu/fisheries/cfp/international/agreements_en

¹⁰ Retrieved from the EU law database <http://eur-lex.europa.eu>

(i.e., Cape Verde, Mauritania, Senegal, and the Seychelles) is presented. This provides an overview of the developments over several generations of agreements related to MCS, including commitments of capacity building and sectoral support. Based on this, the main development and challenges on identified topics will be identified and compared. In conclusion, some considerations of the development in EU external fisheries policy will be made.

The CFP and its external dimension

The fisheries in the EU have since 1983 been governed under the CFP. The CFP has an established ten-year reform cycle, providing EU with regular new and updated fisheries policies in 1992, 2002 and 2013 (the next reform is expected in 2022). The reforms include changes in the idea of and provisions on the external dimension of the EU fishing fleet, as illustrated in Figure 1. Separate regulations for the governance of the external fishing fleets have also been adopted. Today there are three implementing pillars of the external dimension of the CFP: The authorisation of fishing vessels through the Regulation on Sustainable Management of External Fishing Fleets (SMEFF) (repealing the Fisheries Authorisation Regulation (FAR))¹¹, the control of the fisheries based on the Control Regulation¹² applicable to all EU vessels and all fisheries in EU waters, and finally, the efforts to prevent, deter and eliminate IUU fishing based on the IUU Regulation¹³. The latter is a more recent regulation, adopted in 2008, while the other regulations addressing authorisation and control were adopted in 1994 and 1993 respectively, both of which have been amended and repealed several times. Below, the main characteristics and changes related to the governance of the external fishing fleet and bilateral fisheries access agreements are outlined.

¹¹ The SMEFF: Regulation (EU) 2017/2403 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 December 2017 on the sustainable management of external fishing fleets, and repealing Council Regulation (EC) No 1006/2008

The FAR: Council Regulation (EC) No 1006/2008 of 29 September 2008 concerning authorisations for fishing activities of Community fishing vessels outside Community waters and the access of third country vessels to Community waters, amending Regulations (EEC) No 2847/93 and (EC) No 1627/94 and repealing Regulation (EC) No 3317/94

¹² Council Regulation (EC) No 1224/2009 of 20 November 2009 establishing a Community control system for ensuring compliance with the rules of the common fisheries policy, amending Regulations (EC) No 847/96, (EC) No 2371/2002, (EC) No 811/2004, (EC) No 768/2005, (EC) No 2115/2005, (EC) No 2166/2005, (EC) No 388/2006, (EC) No 509/2007, (EC) No 676/2007, (EC) No 1098/2007, (EC) No 1300/2008, (EC) No 1342/2008 and repealing Regulations (EEC) No 2847/93, (EC) No 1627/94 and (EC) No 1966/2006

¹³ Council Regulation (EC) No 1005/2008 of 29 September 2008 establishing a Community system to prevent, deter and eliminate illegal, unreported and unregulated fishing, amending Regulations (EEC) No 2847/93, (EC) No 1936/2001 and (EC) No 601/2004 and repealing Regulations (EC) No 1093/94 and (EC) No 1447/1999

Figure 1 Timeline of the CFP reforms and policy on fisheries access agreements

The first CFPs and the external dimension (1983 and 1992) – Pay-fish-go

The first CFP in 1983¹⁴ provided the legal basis for the EU¹⁵ to enter into fisheries access agreements with third countries, otherwise there was no comprehensive policy on the external dimension. The intention of these agreements was mainly commercial and were generally considered “pay-fish-go” agreements (Sobrino Heredia and Oanta 2015). The reformed CFP in 1992¹⁶ did not result in any major changes to the general policy on fisheries access agreements. It however introduced more detailed rules on fisheries management and MCS, including the vessel licensing system, to apply to all EU vessels, also those operating outside community waters. In the wake of this the Control Regulation¹⁷ and the Fisheries Authorisation Regulation (FAR)¹⁸ were adopted in 1993 and 1994, respectively.

The FAR provided the EU (and the EU flag Member State) with an instrument to ensure that EU vessels fishing in the waters of third countries comply with the terms of the access agreement and with EU rules. The FAR lays down procedures for granting authorization and the communication between the EU, the flag Member States and the partner country.¹⁹ Only fishing vessels that have obtained a fishing licence from the third country can be authorized by the EU flag Member State under the access agreement, and fishing without such a licence are prohibited. The third country can suspend and withdraw a fishing license. The procedures to manage and rules for implementing these are laid down in the Control Regulation.

¹⁴ Council Regulation (EEC) No 170/83 of 25 January 1983 establishing a Community system for the conservation and management of fishery resources.

¹⁵ At the time the EEC (The European Economic Community). In 1993 it became the European Community (EC) and finally the EU in 2009. For simplicity, the term EU is used throughout the paper.

¹⁶ Council Regulation (EEC) No 3760/92 of 20 December 1992 establishing a Community system for fisheries and aquaculture.

¹⁷ Council Regulation (EEC) No 2847/93 of 12 October 1993 establishing a control system applicable to the common fisheries policy

¹⁸ Council Regulation (EEC) No 3317/94 of 22 December 1994 laying down general provisions concerning the authorization of fishing in the waters of a third country under a fisheries agreement

¹⁹ The FAR was developed in line with a parallel Regulation for issuing fishing permits to vessels fishing in EU waters. Council Regulation (EC) No 1627/94 of 27 June 1994 laying down general provisions concerning special fishing permits

It is clearly stated in the Control Regulation that it applies also to EU fishing vessels operating in waters of non-member countries, but without prejudice to the provisions contained in the bilateral agreements between the EU and third countries. Each Member State is therefore obliged to monitor its vessels fishing in external waters according to relevant rules in these waters. The Regulation provides general requirements for inspection and monitoring of fishing vessels and their activities, their catches, use of gear etc., while articles 17 and 18 directly address requirements for Member States to monitor catches from vessels operating in waters of third countries (and on the high seas), their obligation to ensure verification and recordings of transshipments and landings, and to every fourth month notify the Commission the quantities caught and landed, including logbook data, landing declarations from landings in EU ports, transshipment and landing information to third country vessels or -ports. So even though the general objective of access agreements remained the same (pay-fish-go), the EUs instruments to govern their external fleet were substantially strengthened in the 1990's.

The 2002 reform and Fisheries Partnership Agreements (FPAs)

The 2002 CFP reform²⁰ brought a major shift in the framework for fisheries access agreements, and the term Fisheries Partnership Agreements (FPAs) was introduced. The 2002 CFP itself does not mention FPAs, but the obligation for member states to control vessels flying their flag, also when operating outside community waters, was strengthened. The member states shall ensure effective control, inspection and, enforcement of the rules of the CFP, including being responsible for placing observers on board fishing vessels and for taking appropriate decisions, including the prohibition of fishing activities (articles 23 and 24). The framework for FPAs was presented by the Commission in connection with the adoption of the new CFP in December 2002 and adopted in at Council conclusion of 15 July 2004²¹ and subsequently introduced in the new FAR adopted in 2008.²²

The emphasis on partnership and development of sustainable fisheries in the partner countries with the introduction of the FPA was a response to the criticism raised against the access agreements. This brought a new dimension to them, as the agreements now explicitly were to benefit both parties (Le Manach 2014). An important requirement to ensure this was that the EU could only get access to the surplus of allowable catch (that is the part of the allowable catch the coastal State does not have the capacity to harvest, in line with UNCLOS art. 62(4)). The FPAs are emphasising cooperation between the EU and the partner country on fisheries management, MCS and the development of the fisheries

²⁰ Framework Regulation (EC) No 2371/2002 on the conservation and sustainable exploitation of fisheries resources (repealing Regulations (EEC) No 3760/92 and (EEC) No 101/76)

²¹ COUNCIL OF THE EUROPEAN UNION Brussels, 15 July 2004 11485/1/04 REV 1 PECHE 254. Adoption of Council conclusions on a Communication from the Commission on an integrated framework for fisheries partnership agreements with third countries

²² Council Regulation (EC) No 1006/2008 of 29 September 2008 concerning authorisation for fishing activities of Community fishing vessels outside Community waters and the access of third country vessels to Community waters, amending Regulations (EEC) No 2847/93 and (EC) No 1627/94 and repealing Regulation (EC) No 3317/94

sector in the partner country. To that end, sectoral support was introduced, where part of the EU payment should be ear-market to strengthen the capacity of partner countries to manage their fisheries sustainably, in addition to social aspects like requirements on local processing and employment of crew from the partner countries (EC 2009a).

The FAR was repealed in 2008²³, based on the recognition that the Regulation no longer were in line with international obligations and the objectives of the new CFP, in particular regarding sustainable fisheries and control. To improve the control, a Community fishing authorisation information system pursuant to fisheries agreements should be established, on a secure website, ensuring that all data relating to the fishing activities of EU vessels fishing under FPAs should be up-to-date and as far as possible accessible to the Member States and relevant third countries. The authorisation provisions are reinforced, for instance by only allowing authorisation of vessels which have not been subject to sanction proceedings for serious infringements or considered suspect of such breaches the last 12 months, and which are not included in an RFMO IUU list. The Regulation now also includes a section on electronic reporting of catches (or fishing efforts), with reference to the new Regulations on electronic recording and reporting of fishing activities adopted in 2006²⁴, requiring daily reporting to national authorities from 1 January 2010 for vessels over 24 meters, and from 1 January 2011 for vessels over 15 meters. The flag Member States shall on a monthly basis submit by electronic submission data for each stock or fishing category on the quantities caught under FPAs. More details are provided in the new Control Regulation.

The new Control Regulation was adopted in 2009²⁵. By then, the European Fisheries Control Agency (EFCA) was established (in Spain in 2005)²⁶ to ensure more effective, transparent, and fair monitoring of the EU fishing fleets. In addition, the Regulations on electronic recording and reporting and remote

²³ Council Regulation (EC) No 1006/2008 of 29 September 2008 concerning authorisation for fishing activities of Community fishing vessels outside Community waters and the access of third country vessels to Community waters, amending Regulations (EEC) No 2847/93 and (EC) No 1627/94 and repealing Regulation (EC) No 3317/94

²⁴ Council Regulation (EC) No 1966/2006 of 21 December 2006 on electronic recording and reporting of fishing activities and on means of remote sensing; Commission Regulation (EC) No 1566/2007 of 21 December 2007 laying down detailed rules for the implementation of Council Regulation (EC) No 1966/2006 on electronic recording and reporting of fishing activities and on means of remote sensing

²⁵ COUNCIL REGULATION (EC) No 1224/2009 of 20 November 2009 establishing a Community control system for ensuring compliance with the rules of the common fisheries policy, amending Regulations (EC) No 847/96, (EC) No 2371/2002, (EC) No 811/2004, (EC) No 768/2005, (EC) No 2115/2005, (EC) No 2166/2005, (EC) No 388/2006, (EC) No 509/2007, (EC) No 676/2007, (EC) No 1098/2007, (EC) No 1300/2008, (EC) No 1342/2008 and repealing Regulations (EEC) No 2847/93, (EC) No 1627/94 and (EC) No 1966/2006

²⁶ COUNCIL REGULATION (EC) No 768/2005 of 26 April 2005 establishing a Community Fisheries Control Agency and amending Regulation (EEC) No 2847/93 establishing a control system applicable to the common fisheries policy

sensing that had been adopted (in 2006 and 2007)²⁷ were now repealed. The IUU Regulation²⁸ was adopted in 2008. All these instruments called for a substantial strengthening of the MCS of EU vessels. The obligation of Member States' fisheries monitoring centres to monitor the fishing vessels flying their flag in whatever the waters they operate or port they are in, are strengthened. All EU vessels should operate a vessel monitoring systems (VMS) from 2012 at the latest, also those operating in waters of a third country, and the data should be made available to the third country if provided by the agreement. Bigger vessels shall have an automatic identification system (AIS), applicable from 2012 to 2014 depending on length (more than 24 meters to 15 meters). The Control Regulation also provides detailed provisions on (electronic) completion and transmission of logbook data, prior notification of landings and transshipment, and on (electronic) completion and transmission of landing declaration data, in addition to provisions on inspections also in waters outside community waters. Two implementing control regulations have been adopted based on the 2009 regulation, in 2011²⁹ and 2015³⁰, providing detailed rules to ensure compliance with the CFP and the Community control system.

The 2013 reform and the Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreements (SFPAs)

Despite the improvement in the terms and conditions for the fisheries access agreements following the CFP 2002 reform and new implementing Regulations, many issues were still found to be unsatisfactory with the regulation of the external EU fleet. As a response, the 2013 CFP reform³¹ provided a new approach to the access fisheries agreements with the introduction of SFPAs. SFPAs and the external dimension of the EU fisheries policy was now included as a separate chapter in the CFP (part VI, art. 28-33), where it is emphasised that fishing outside and inside EU waters should be based on the same principles and standards. The focus on partnership and local development are continued from the FPA to the SFPA framework. The main change in the external policy is the obligations to better control fisheries taking place outside SFPAs. The main improvement was the extension of the fishing authorisation system to also include private agreements and reflagged EU vessels, not only the public agreements. This create a common set of criteria that must be fulfilled for all vessels to obtain a fishing

²⁷ COUNCIL REGULATION (EC) No 1966/2006 of 21 December 2006 on electronic recording and reporting of fishing activities and on means of remote sensing; COMMISSION REGULATION (EC) No 1566/2007 of 21 December 2007 laying down detailed rules for the implementation of Council Regulation (EC) No 1966/2006 on electronic recording and reporting of fishing activities and on means of remote sensing

²⁸ Council Regulation (EC) No 1005/2008 of 29 September 2008 establishing a Community system to prevent, deter and eliminate illegal, unreported and unregulated fishing, amending Regulations (EEC) No 2847/93, (EC) No 1936/2001 and (EC) No 601/2004 and repealing Regulations (EC) No 1093/94 and (EC) No 1447/1999

²⁹ Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) No 404/2011 of 8 April 2011 laying down detailed rules for the implementation of Council Regulation (EC) No 1224/2009 establishing a Community control system for ensuring compliance with the rules of the Common Fisheries Policy

³⁰ Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2015/1962 of 28 October 2015 amending Implementing Regulation (EU) No 404/2011 laying down detailed rules for the implementation of Council Regulation (EC) No 1224/2009 establishing a Community control system for ensuring compliance with the rules of the common fisheries policy

³¹ Council Regulation (EU) No 1380/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2013 on the Common Fisheries Policy, amending Council Regulations (EC) No 1954/2003 and (EC) No 1224/2009 and repealing Council Regulations (EC) No 2371/2002 and (EC) No 639/2004 and Council Decision 2004/585/EC.

authorisation to fish outside community waters. In addition, EU vessels are no longer allowed to operate in a partner country outside the framework of a SFPA, by the so-called exclusivity clause. Transparency should also be improved through a publicly available registry about the external fleet, providing information about which vessel are fishing for what and where. A new issue in the 2013 CFP is bycatch and discard, which is also reflected in the 2011 and 2015 Control Regulations.

In the wake of the 2013 CFP, the FAR in 2017 was repealed by a new Authorisation Regulation, the Regulation on Sustainable Management of External Fishing Fleets (SMEFF)³². The main change from the FAR is that it provides more transparency and lay the ground for better monitoring and control of the external fishing fleet. Transparency is provided by adding a public part to the secure electronic fishing authorisation database, making some non-sensitive information about the authorised vessels openly accessible. The control of the external fishing fleet is improved by now including transshipment, chartering, reflagging and direct authorisations (fishing in third party waters outside SFPAs, i.e., private agreements). Transshipment taking place on the high seas or under direct authorisations should be reported. The monitoring of support vessels aims at improving control of fishing operations and catches, whereas monitoring of reflagging operations shall make the EU able to detect and hamper operations to circumvent CFP rules and existing conservation and management measures. Vessels that have reflagged to a third country the last five years without being able to verify this and that it has not been engaged in IUU fishing should not be authorised.

With reference to the Control Regulation, there is a requirement to the exchange of data in electronic form between the Member States and the Commission, and also third parties, and the need to coordinate those activities are stated. The SMEFF also clarify some administrative roles between Member States and the Commission, and some reporting obligations. In addition, there is a chapter on the obligation of the vessel to report data from observer programs to the flag Member State, as well as catch and landing declarations to the third country with a copy to the flag Member State. The Member State has an obligation to cross-check this data and ensure that it is in accordance with the Control Regulation and relevant provisions of the SFPA. Failure to do so should be considered serious infringements and be handled according to the procedures laid down in the Control Regulation. A proposal for a new Control Regulation was presented in May 2018³³, but is yet to be adopted. The main changes here are related to the response to infringements.

³² The SMEFF: Regulation (EU) 2017/2403 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 December 2017 on the sustainable management of external fishing fleets, and repealing Council Regulation (EC) No 1006/2008

The FAR: Council Regulation (EC) No 1006/2008 of 29 September 2008 concerning authorisations for fishing activities of Community fishing vessels outside Community waters and the access of third country vessels to Community waters, amending Regulations (EEC) No 2847/93 and (EC) No 1627/94 and repealing Regulation (EC) No 3317/94

³³ Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL amending Council Regulation (EC) No 1224/2009, and amending Council Regulations (EC) No 768/2005, (EC) No 1967/2006, (EC) No 1005/2008, and Regulation (EU) No 2016/1139 of the European Parliament and of the Council as regards fisheries control, Brussels, 30.5.2018 COM(2018) 368 final 2018/0193 (COD)

The question then is how the EU has been able to implement its policy on the external dimension of the CFP related to MCS of fisheries taking place under access agreements.

The fisheries access agreements analysed

Today there are 13 SFPAs in force, 9 tuna agreements and 4 multi-species or so-called mixed agreements.³⁴ The main tuna species are skipjack and yellowfin, but some of the agreements also give access to albacore and bigeye, in addition to other large pelagic species like billfishes and sharks. The non-tuna agreements include species like crustaceans, cephalopods, small pelagic and demersal fish, like hake.

The access agreements consist of three parts; the Agreement itself which determines the scope and basic principles of the agreement, the Protocol which authorizes fishing access of EU vessels and specifies fishing opportunities, amounts and methods of payments, and finally the pertaining Annexes which sets out implementation and procedural aspects such as the licensing system, electronic catch reporting, vessel monitoring systems, observers, and control and enforcement.³⁵ For each access agreement, a Joint Scientific Committee with representatives from the European Commission and partner country authorities monitor the performance and interpretation of the agreement. It also has the competence to approve amendments regarding fishing opportunities, financial contribution, sectoral support procedures and any other technical provisions. Finally, the mentioned ex-post/ex-ante evaluations are informing the parties before renegotiating a new agreement.

The access agreements are re-negotiated regularly. In this study, the development in the access agreements has been analysed over a long time period, and includes all parts of the agreements (i.e., the Agreements, Protocols and associated Annexes). The Agreement itself is often negotiated as renewable, resulting in one Agreement covering several Protocols. In the remaining we refer to these as the Agreement and Protocol, while use access agreement or just agreement when referring to the agreement as a whole.

Table 1 provide an overview of the current fishing opportunities and financial compensation in the four access agreements analysed.

³⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/fisheries/cfp/international/agreements_en

³⁵ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/c8b5d962-0d38-11e7-8a35-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-37907030>

Table 1 Main characteristic of the current Agreements with Cape Verde, Mauritania, Senegal, and the Seychelles³⁶

	Cape Verde	Mauritania*	Senegal	Seychelles
Species	Tuna	Multi-species	Tuna and hake	Tuna
Reference tonnage per year	8 000	Crustaceans 5 000 Hake 9 500 Other demersal 3 000 Pelagic 240 000 Tuna 20 000	Tuna 10 000 Hake 1 750	50 000
Financial contribution: Annual payment	€550 000 - 500 000	€61 625 000	€1 700 000	€5 300 000
Part for sectoral support	€350 000	€4 125 000	€900 000	€2 800 000
Fee for ship owners, per tonne caught	€55-65	Crustaceans €400 Hake €70-90 Squid €575 Cuttlefish €250 Bycatches €90 Other demersal €105 Pelagic €123 Tuna €60-70	Tuna €75-85 Hake €95	€80-85
No. of vessels	69 vessels 28 purse seiners 27 longliners 14 pole-and-liners Spain 45 vessels, France 16 vessels Portugal 8 vessels	98 vessels 25 crustaceans 6 hake trawlers 6 demersal 25 tuna seiners 15 tune pole-and-liners 21 pelagic trawlers Crustaceans: Spain, Italy and Portugal Hake: Spain Tuna: Spain and France Pelagic: main countries Lithuania, Latvia, Poland and Netherland	45 vessels 28 tuna seiners 10 pole-and-liners 5 longliners 2 trawlers Spain 29 vessels France 16 vessels	48 vessels 40 tuna seiners 8 longliners Spain 24 vessels France 20 vessels Italy 2 vessels Portugal 2 vessels

*The numbers are summarized. In the Agreement the fishing opportunities (tonnes/year) for different species are more detailed for different vessels groups, as is the fees for ship owners, number of vessels allowed for each fishery, the number of licences or tonnes for each country, number of vessels allowed in Mauritanian waters at any one time.

³⁶ Source [Sustainable fisheries partnership agreements \(SFPAs\) \(europa.eu\)](https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/tgm/table.do?tab=table&init=1&language=en&plugin=1), downloaded 22nd April 2021

The development of the MCS in the four fisheries access agreements

The topic under scrutiny in this study is the development over time of the EU access agreements, currently termed SFPAs, and whether the changes observed follow the development enshrined in the reforms of the CFP and regulations of the EU external fishing fleet.

The oldest access agreement analysed is the one with Senegal from 1979. This was the first bilateral fisheries access agreements concluded by the EU. It was running continuously until 2006, when the parties did not agree on a new agreement. This was first reached in 2013 after the revision of the CFP, and the new agreement and accompanying protocol entered into force in 2014. Hence, no fishing was taking place in Senegalese waters under a bilateral agreement in the years 2007-2013.³⁷ Later, EU and Senegal adopted a new Agreement for 2014-2019, which was tacitly renewed to 2024, leading to the latest Protocol agreed in 2019 for a period of 5 years, expiring in 2024. The access agreements with both Mauritania and Seychelles date back to 1987. However, the status of these is very different. In 2020 a new Agreement with Seychelles was signed. It is a 6-years renewable Agreement lasting to 2026. This is an SFPA, entirely rewritten and not only a prolongation of the existing FPA. The Protocol is also renegotiated and is running for the same period. The Mauritanian Agreement, on the other hand, has not been rewritten since 2006, and technically this agreement is therefore an FPA. However, the Protocol that entered into force in 2015-2019 is based on the SFPA framework. While negotiations to establish a new long-term agreement are taking place, this Protocol has been extended twice for one year at a time and is currently valid until November 2021. The newest access agreement analysed is the one with Cape Verde, which was first agreed in 1990. Like Mauritania, the current Agreement is technically an FPA, as it has been tacitly renewed since 2007, but also this Protocol is based on the SFPA framework. The newest Protocol was agreed in 2019 with a 5-years duration, to 2024. Even if the prolonged Agreements with Mauritania and Cape Verde still are named FPAs, the whole agreements (Agreement, Protocol and Annexes) are referred to as SFPA as the Protocols have been renewed and negotiated under this framework.

The review of the different generations of access agreements shows a clear trend. The first access agreements were substantially shorter and less detailed than the later ones. Still, they already contained the main provisions we find in the current access agreements, like requirements for license application and payment, catch and landing notification and reporting, requirements for observers, employment of seamen, and procedures to follow in case of detection of infringements and on sanctions. It is in particular the Protocols and Annexes that have become more detailed. Some new issues are addressed, like IUU-fishing, and new concepts are introduced, like transparency, sustainability, partnership, and sectoral support.

³⁷ However, some tuna vessels were operating under private agreements or under joint ventures in the period.

This section provides an analysis of the main developments and changes of the four access agreements related to MCS and how they “mirror” the development in the EU policy on the external dimension of the EU fishing fleet. The development is assessed along three main areas: changes in the provisions on authorisation of fishing vessels, new procedures and technologies for improved MCS, and new modes of cooperation between the parties. The formal requirements do not necessarily reflect the performance under the agreements, as there might be lack of or insufficient implementation. How identified implementation challenges are handled when renegotiating the Agreements and Protocols therefore shed light on the process of changing the access agreements in line with the developments in the CFP.

Authorization of fishing vessels

Authorization of fishing vessels is a key instrument to regulate access to fisheries and a central part of the CFP, where the provisions have been strengthened over time. As an EU Regulation, the Fishing Authorization Regulation (FAR and later SMEFF) is directly applicable to the member states, but (obviously) not on non-member states. Still, we find that the authorisation provisions in the access agreements to a high degree reflect the development in the FAR/SMEFF. In the first access agreements, the authorisation provisions address the practical arrangement between the EU and partner authorities. Provisions on the vessels itself, its master or owner and their conduct in the partner country, are included in the Protocols from the early- 2000s, requiring vessels to have fulfilled all prior obligations arising from their fishing activities in the area to be able to gain an authorisation. A major change in the 2008 FAR regulation is the emphasis on IUU-fishing, where vessels sanctioned for serious infringements or listed on an RFMO IUU lists are not to be authorized. This is also reflected in the access agreements renegotiated at this time. Although not using the term IUU fishing, the Seychelles Protocol 2010-2013 refers to the 2008 FAR articles where this is emphasised. In the newest Protocols of all the four access agreements, requirements are directly linked to IUU fishing, for instance in the Mauritania Protocol from 2015 and the Seychelles Protocol from 2020, where it is explicitly stated that vessel listed on an RFMO IUU-list are not to be authorised. The SMEFF, adopted in 2017, introduced provisions on increased transparency about the access agreements and the vessels authorised. The authorisation provision in two of the four access agreements to a high degree follow the development in the EU regulation. The Senegalese Protocol from 2019 contains some general provisions on the parties’ commitment to transparency and good governance as well as an obligation to make public and exchange relevant information on fishing activities pertaining the Protocol. In the most recent Agreement with Seychelles, there is an obligation to make public, and exchange, data on activity from authorized vessels. However, neither in the Cape Verde Protocol negotiated after the adoption of the SMEFF, nor the one from Mauritanian adopted in 2015 and which has been tacitly renewed since then, mention transparency.

MCS

While the authorisation provisions set the standards and procedures for attaining, or losing, the right to fish in the partner country, a central part of the Protocols provide provision on the monitoring and control of the fisheries, including how to cooperate to improve the MCS of these fisheries.

The Control Regulation, first adopted in 1993, required member states to monitor catches from vessels operating outside EU waters and to verify and report quantities caught, based on logbook data, and transshipment- and landing declarations. We find the same requirements in the access agreements from that period, where community vessels are obliged to complete a fishing form with catch details and send it to the authorities in the partner country with copies to scientific institutions as well as to the flag state.

In the 2000s the EU adopted a number of regulations to improve the MCS of its fisheries, including the Regulations on electronic recording and reporting, the IUU Regulation and a new Control Regulation. Electronic tools to monitor fishing activities were now generally introduced, and in the 2009 Control Regulation it is established that from 2012 all bigger vessels flying the flag of a member country are required to operate a VMS “wherever those vessels may be”. VMS is today mandatory in all the four access agreements. In the Seychelles agreement, VMS was introduced to monitor community vessels in 2002, but provisions and guidelines were not developed until the 2005 Protocol. VMS was also mentioned in the Senegalese Agreement from 2002, but only in relation to the financial contribution to improve MCS. In the next Agreement from 2014 VMS was made mandatory. In Mauritania VMS was first mentioned in 2006, to facilitate and prepare for implementation. In 2012 it was introduced as a requirement. This is also the case for Cape Verde where VMS was first introduced in 2006 with a decision to adopt provisions on VMS in the first year of the Protocol. The provisions were added as an appendix, and subsequently included as a requirement in the Protocol itself when it was renewed in 2011. Hence, in the years 2012-2013 VMS was included as separate sections in the Protocols of all four access agreements. Requirements and specifications have become more detailed since then. We therefore see a gradual introduction of VMS in all the access agreements, where it is first proposed and then followed up by concrete guidelines before making it mandatory. AIS were made mandatory for EU vessels from 2012-2014, depending on the vessel length. There is no direct mention of AIS in the four access agreements, and hence no obligation for the EU vessels to transmit such data to the partner countries.

According to the EU regulation, electronic reporting and recording (ERS) were to be implemented by 2010/2011. In the access agreements however, introducing ERS has been slow. All the access agreements are moving towards more electronic monitoring and reporting, but the introduction is progressing unevenly. In Seychelles and Cape Verde ERS was introduced in the 2014 Protocols. These were statements of intent to introduce ERS, but without any guidelines on how to implement it. ERS

was also a topic in the Senegalese Protocol from 2014, but more implicit as vessels only were encouraged to report electronically. In the latest Protocols negotiated with the three countries in 2019 and 2020, ERS is included as a requirement, and guidelines for implementation and transition are attached. As with the introduction of VMS, we see a gradual introduction, and even though it is mandatory the parties are still committed to “define common arrangements to ensure that the transition takes place as soon as possible”. Mauritania is the only access agreement where ERS is not yet included. The current Protocol was adopted in 2015 and has as recalled been tacitly renewed pending the conclusion of a new Agreement.

Observation of fishing activities is an important aspect in scientific data collection but is also used for control purposes. In the 2009 Control Regulation the term control observer was introduced, referring to a person authorized by a national authority to monitor the fishing vessel’s compliance with the rules of the CFP. A Union control observer scheme is to be established, and in the proposal for amending the Control Regulation it is suggested to make these rules applicable also in the waters of third countries in which a Union vessel is operating.³⁸ In the four access agreements the observers’ duties are mainly for scientific purposes, and it is only in the Mauritanian Protocol it is explicitly stated that the observers shall ensure that the Union vessels operating in the Mauritanian fishing zone comply with the terms of the Protocol. The Seychelles Protocol from 2020 is the only one including electronic observation schemes (as a part of respecting the obligations of relevant IOTC resolutions). Despite this, observers have been required already in the first access agreements of all the cases. All EU vessels are obliged to take on board observers designated by the partner country through their observer programmes. Around 2005 the requirements for the observer routines became more detailed for both parties, with descriptions of observer duties, embarkation, and reporting routines. Only minor changes are added after that. For Senegal, which did not have an access agreement between 2006 and 2014, this was introduced in the new access agreement of 2014. The observer chapter in the Mauritanian Protocol differs slightly from the others in the format. The content is the same, but the level of detail is somewhat less. This is however the only Protocol where the requirements have been eased, from requiring observers on all vessels to only requiring on board two vessels per fishing category per year. As will be described below, in all the access agreements there are challenges related to implementing the observer requirement.

Another way of increasing control with the fisheries is by improving the reporting and monitoring of transshipment. In the EU, reporting obligations were introduced in the 2002 CFP and included in the Regulation on electronic reporting of 2006. In the new Control Regulation of 2009 transshipment at sea was prohibited in Community waters, only allowing it in designated ports, and with requirements on prior notice and accompanying inspection procedures. In the four access agreements, the prohibition to tranship at sea and obligation to designate ports for transshipment was however introduced already

³⁸ https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/A-9-2021-0016_EN.html

in the first half of the decade. Actually, transshipment was mentioned in the Mauritanian access agreement already in 1996, addressing freezer trawlers but without any mandatory provisions. For each renewal of the Mauritanian Protocol the requirements have been strengthened, from setting a number of transshipments to be done in Mauritanian ports, to finally making it mandatory in 2006. In 2015, a provision was included to designate a local agent for landings and transshipments. As such, the access agreements preceded the EU regulations.

The obligation to only tranship in port allows for increased level of physical inspections. Inspection is a central, but resource demanding, instrument in fisheries control, especially at sea. In the 2009 Control Regulation there is a focus on establishing procedures and routines for inspections and inspection reports. In the access agreements for Cape Verde, Mauritania, Senegal, and Seychelles this is addressed in the years 2011, 2012, 2014 and 2020, respectively. Union vessels fishing under these access agreements shall allow inspectors from the respective partner country to come on board and carry out their work. The Protocols provide detailed guidelines for how the inspections shall be carried out and how they shall be reported, and these have become more detailed in the later protocols, in line with the developments in the Control Regulation.

In the mid-2000s IUU fishing was high on the EU agenda and were included in several of the EU regulations. Before 2014, IUU-fishing was not explicitly mentioned in the access agreements. In the 2014 Protocol for Senegal and the 2020 Protocol for Seychelles, the issue was added in a section called participatory monitoring in the fight against IUU-fishing. By this, Union vessels are obliged to report sighted vessels operating in the areas without a license or vessels engaged in activities that may constitute IUU fishing. In these countries, the importance of cooperation in the fight against IUU-fishing is also visible in the Agreement itself, as it is explicitly stated that the parties shall cooperate in this area. In the other two Agreements, IUU is not an issue in the Agreements.

Another challenge first addressed by the EU in the early 2010s is bycatch and discards. This was first included as a topic in the 2013 CFP but was already a topic in the 2011 Implementing Control Regulation. The focus has been on bycatch and discards in Community waters, where a landing obligation with a gradual implementation for different fisheries has been adopted. Relating to the external fishing fleet, the issue has generally been handled by relevant RFMOs. The issue is handled differently in the four access agreements. There is a clear difference between the three tuna agreements and the multi-species agreement with Mauritania. The tuna fisheries are taking place under the fisheries regulations and reporting requirements of the two tuna RFMOs IOTC and ICCAT. These are not explicitly mentioned in the access agreements, but in recent years the topic of bycatch and discards is to a certain degree handled. Bycatch was not addressed in the first access agreement with Cape Verde of 1991, besides mentioning that vessels should “wherever possible, make part of their bycatch available to the fishing authorities”. A similar phrase is later included in the Seychelles

agreement. The Cape Verde agreement requires the vessels to report bycatch of turtles and shark. In the most recent Agreement, the requirements for reporting bycatch of blue sharks have become more detailed. The background for this is that blue shark had become the target species in the catches of tuna-longliners, comprising around 70% of catches even though it was not listed as a target species. This was changed in the latest protocol adopted in 2019. The Senegalese agreement contains technical measures to reduce bycatch, particularly from 2014, when it was included as a relevant part into the observer tasks. In Seychelles this topic is not handled in detail in the access agreements, but vessels are required to verify and report bycatch. The requirements on bycatch and discard for the tuna agreements are therefore influenced more by the developments in the relevant RFMOs, of which the partner countries are parties. In the Mauritanian agreement the focus has been on establishing reporting procedures for bycatch. The problem of discards was acknowledged already in 2006, and in 2008 it was termed dumping and sea pollution. Detailed reporting requirement for bycatches was however first included in the 2012 protocol, when bycatches were included in the fishing datasheets from each fishing category. In the latest Protocols, there is no specific mention of the topic, but it seems to be covered by targeted allocation of funds for cooperation and capacity building on environmental issues, and the monitoring, reporting and observer program.

Cooperation on MCS

The move away from a purely economic transaction with the pay-fish-go agreements to access agreements based on partnership and cooperation constitute an important change in the external dimension of the CFP. The 2002 reform of the CFP and the introduction of the Fisheries Partnership Agreements (FPA) therefore impacted on both the standards for interaction between the partners and approach to ensure MCS of the fisheries. In Mauritania, this shift was visible already in 1996 when the wording in the Agreement changed from an agreement giving access to “fishing off” the coast of Mauritania to a “cooperation agreement”. The next Agreement of 2006, was labelled an FPA, as is all the access agreements the EU has negotiated after the 2002 CFP reform. In general, the focus on cooperation in the access agreements have increased in line with the development in the CFP. For instance, in Senegal cooperation was not mentioned in 2002, but in the new SFPA of 2014 this area is a central part of the Agreement, among other stating that ‘the Agreement establishes the principles, rules and procedures governing cooperation on the arrangements for monitoring fisheries in Senegalese waters...’. In the other cases, with running access agreements, this shift to emphasise cooperation is clearly visible in the Agreements from 2006, and in the subsequent Protocols.

A body gaining increased importance in the agreements when moving towards increased cooperation is the Joint Scientific Committee, a committee made up of representatives from both EU and the partner country. In Cape Verde and Seychelles, the Joint Committee was first mentioned in 2001-2002 related to the review of payments in the light of implementation. In 2006 however, there is a shift in both the access agreements as the role of the Joint Committee is described in more detail in the

Agreement and referred to in the Protocol with regards to scientific cooperation and revision of the Protocol. It is also stated that the parties shall agree on multiannual sectoral programmes and rules for implementation and also consult on issues on mutual interest. This trend continues in the next Protocols. The same trend is seen in the other two access agreements, but in Mauritania the role of the Joint Committee was described briefly already in 1996. In the new Protocol from 2006 we see a clear shift where the role of the Joint Committee is strengthened and its mandate to decide on matters regarding the provision in the Protocol is clarified, including the allocation of the sectoral support funds. In Senegal this trend starts in 2002, but the main shift is in 2014 when a new Agreement is signed.

One important instrument for increased cooperation, introduced in the 2002 CFP is sectoral support, and the Joint Committees have a central part in the planning for and monitoring of the implementation and use of the funds. The aim is to strengthen the capacity of partner countries to manage their fisheries sustainably. In the analysed access agreements, the issue was first introduced in the period 2001-2005. The Protocols serve as a guide for the priority of the use of the sectoral support, where improved MCS capacity is listed as one of the priority areas in all the access agreements. A key area is capacity building efforts. The guidelines and requirement for the use of the funding has become more detailed for each Protocol. The Joint Committee in Mauritania is granted decision making over these funds which arguably, gives more control to both parts on the resource allocation, while the allocation of funding is stated in the Senegalese Protocol. A new area of cooperation is physical inspection. This area was not addressed in any of the access agreements until 2020, when it was introduced in the Seychelles SFP. It was termed 'cooperation in the area of MCS and the fight against IUU fishing'. Here it is stated that the parties may agree to cooperate on and carry out joint inspection programmes on Union vessels to ensure compliance with both Union and Seychelles legislation. In the other access agreements, cooperation on inspections is limited to authorizing representatives from the EU to participate as an observer. This possibility was introduced in the period 2010 to 2015 in all the four access agreements. Mauritania is an exception, where there is a mutual system for shore-based controls. Here both parties shall designate representatives who shall attend monitoring operations and inspections with the aim of observing the implementation of the Protocol. This system was introduced already in 2006 and was extended to include controls both on land and at sea in 2015.

The review shows that the MCS requirements in the access agreements are continuously being strengthened and becoming more detailed. At the same time there are recognized implementation challenges. These generally relates to insufficient technical and human capacity and are addressed in the ex-post- ex ante evaluations, in addition to being a task for the Joint Committees. To a certain degree implementation challenges are reflected in the access agreements themselves, through changes in requirements and increased focus on an issue. Others are less visible when analysing the development of the agreements per se. The introduction of the obligation for vessels to operate a VMS

is a good example of how a new MCS instrument is gradually being introduced. First the requirement is introduced, then provisions and guidelines are later developed. Another example of how a challenge is handled in the access agreements is on sectoral support. In all the partner countries there are challenges related to implementation of the agreed MCS capacity building efforts. Poor reporting routines have made it difficult to monitor the use of the sectoral support and the transparency on the use of the financial contribution have been low. More detailed requirements and stricter reporting routines have been added to new Protocols, illustrating the effort to overcome some of these challenges. The exception is the agreement with Mauritania, where the use of these resources was made less detailed from 2001 to 2006. It might however be questioned whether the changes in reporting routines are made to improve the economic control rather than to improve the capacity building efforts. A well-known challenge in all the fisheries that is not reflected in the access agreements is the low observer coverage and lack of trained observers. This is a recurring issue in the ex-post- ex ante evaluations. The requirement for observer coverage in the access agreements however stays unchanged, despite decades of non-fulfilment of reaching the required observer level. We rather observe that new Protocols provide admittedly more detailed provisions for embarkation conditions, and observers' duties and obligations. For the tuna-agreements the non-fulfilment of the observer coverage requirement can partly be explained by the observer requirements in ICCAT and IOTC, which are also referred to in the three tuna access agreements. In the Mauritania access agreement, where shared fisheries are not managed by an RFMO, the situation is slightly different, and this is the only access agreement where the observer challenge to a certain degree is reflected.³⁹ In 2012 the requirement was eased from observers being required on board all EU vessels to at least two designated vessels for each fishing category per year.

While some measures are adapted to the capacity of the partner country to implement a requirement, others directly linked to implementation of control requirements are not eased. For instance, all the partner countries experience technical problems both with VMS and ERS, mainly due to lack of technical resources, but also human resources to handle the information received. Still, the access agreements are continuously moving forward with stricter requirements on the use of electronic monitoring and control. In this case, it is fair to say that the access agreements as such do not reflect the challenges identified. On the other hand, the capacity building initiatives under the sectoral support and the multiannual sectoral programme and rules for implementing must be considered efforts to improve implementation of the MCS requirements of the agreements, and as such the challenges are addressed in the agreements. There are also some training initiatives to strengthen MSC

³⁹ There is however a Regional Fisheries Body, the Fisheries Committee for the Eastern Central Atlantic (CECAF), which have a purely advisory status, of which both the EU and Mauritania are parties. The CECAF amongst other encourage and coordinate research, provide advice on MCS and encourage and coordinate training in areas of interest to the Committee.

tools through other cross-border cooperation, like the *Pescao*⁴⁰ project. This project is amongst other working on the implementation of a regional observer's network to improve the monitoring of the industrial fleet operating in western Africa.

Conclusion

The analysis of the development of MCS requirements in the four access agreements with Cape Verde, Mauritania, Senegal, and the Seychelles reveals that the provisions on MCS have been substantially improved. There is a clear strengthening in the MCS provisions in the EU access agreements over time. The provisions generally follow the development in the CFP and accompanying implementing regulations, in some cases also preceding the enshrinement in EU regulations. At the same time, there is a natural delay in implementation of new policies where the Agreements and Protocols remain under the framework of earlier CFPs until they are re-negotiated. Not surprisingly, a major change occurs with the introduction of FPA in the 2002 reform of the CFP. Both the form, content, and level of detail in the Agreements and Protocols negotiated after this clearly reflects new governing ideas and a commitment to better monitor this fleet. The general technological development and introduction of electronic monitoring and reporting of fishing activities is also reflected in the access agreements. Sustainability is introduced as an overarching principle and provisions to promote this in relation to MCS is increased cooperation, information sharing and detailed requirements on monitoring and reporting of catches and how to handle infringements. The trend is that EU is becoming more and more engaged in the partner countries, amongst other illustrated by the increased importance of the Joint Committees, and the introduction of the sectoral support and the multiannual sectoral programs. However, there are clear differences between the four access agreements. Especially the agreement with Mauritania does not always follow the same pattern as the others. Several issues are introduced earlier in this agreement than the others, and adjustments are made to accommodate the situation in Mauritania. As a non-tuna agreement, all MCS measures in the Mauritanian case must also be included directly in the access agreement and does not rely on or are bind by an RFMO. There are also among the other agreements. For instance, in relation to IUU-fishing. In the newest access agreements, the focus on IUU-fishing is more present in the Seychelles and the Senegalese agreement than in the others. So even though the four access agreements follow the general developments in the CFP, they also differ and stands out as individual agreements reflecting differences in the fisheries and challenges faced in each case.

Despite the progress, the analysis shows that even though there is a positive development in the MSC requirements in the agreements, the implementation of new requirements can be slow. An example is the gradual introduction and slow implementation of VMS and ERS. So even if new Agreements and

⁴⁰ <https://www.efca.europa.eu/en/content/pescao>

Protocols are in line with the new reformed CFPs and implementation regulations, this does not necessarily mean that the new requirements are implemented. Sometimes it takes several protocols from a requirement is first introduced before it is implemented, other times it does not get implemented. The observer requirement is an example of the latter, where a persistent demand for a high level of observers onboard the EU vessels are maintained over decades (in three of the four cases) but without the partners, so far, being able to address the underlying challenge of ensuring sufficient number of observers. On the one hand, this gradual and slow implementation might therefore be a viable approach and way for the EU to be able to implement its external fisheries policy, in particular when accompanied with capacity building initiatives and increased cooperation. On the other hand, if the MCS requirements are not implemented, and are not adjusted to the actual situation, they may end up as paper-regulations which over time will undermine the credibility of the access agreements.

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